

Estimating the water budget components and their variability in a Pre-Alpine basin with JGrass-NewAGE: supplementary material

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This document provides supplementary information to "Estimating the water budget components and their variability in a Pre-Alpine basin with JGrass-NewAGE", *Advances in Water Resources*, 2016:136. We present here, in section one a selection of water budget studies, in section 2, we give information about the data set we used. In section 3 we give a simplified sketch of the model setup. Section 4 contains the list of Object Modelling System components we have used. Section 5 contains some further information about the MODIS data that were used in the paper. Finally, in section 6, we give a synthesis of the Adige rainfall-runoff model.

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1. WATER BUDGET STUDIES

The list below, certainly to be cleaned, improved and enriched, says that there are effectively many papers (out of around a hundred-twenty we inspected) that do it. They are distributed according to four threads.

- The one of "global and continental hydrology" where the water budget of the whole earth or of the largest river basins is studied. The methods used are remote sensing data, global circulation models, atmospheric reanalysis, large-scale hydrological models.
- One thread is (but the focus is more often on evaporation) based on the use of Budyko curves, at various scales.
- One thread is based upon the use of models plus in-situ data, with various degrees of simplification models are process-based (like CATHY, GEOTop or ParFlow, to cite three of them) or more conceptualised (as our JGrass-NewAGE). Data are the most various, depending on the spatial scale of the application and the type of model. Process-based models use more data (which is a richness or a weakness, depending on the point of view), while conceptual models use less data. Larger scale applications require a coarse gaining of the data set and, obviously, a limitation in the description of spatial heterogeneity.
- Finally there are fully experimental papers, especially in forest and agricultural areas, with accurate measurements, for some specific plant stand, or even single trees.

Table S1. Table of papers estimating the water budget at different spatial and time scales

Study	Method (model)	Spatial Scale	Time span resolution	Location
[1]	Satellite, VIC model	87498 - 409298 km ²	annual (daily)	Arkansas-Red River
[2]	In situ data (groundwater)-20110-2012	1.6 km ² and 3.4 km ²	Hourly to annual	south-Western Victoria, Australia
[3]	Modeling (SWAT)	122-248 km ²	Annual (1951-1957)	Illinois, U.S.
[4]	Satellite data	Daily (September 2002-December 2006); large scale	Monthly	Amazon basin
[5]	Modeling (WetSpass); In situ measurements	694-1677 km ²	Monthly-Yearly	Belgium
[6]	Modeling; In situ measurements	9 Km ² and 603 km ²	hourly	Trento, Italy; Oklahoma, U.S.
[7]	In situ measures	sites in a 2.5 km ² area	Annual (weekly), 1995-1998	arlington Agricultural Research Station, WI, U.S.
[8]	In situ observation (Precip, incoming shortwave radiation, Air temperature, vapor pressure, atmospheric pressure, wind speed, runoff etc)	38.52 ha small, forested subcatchment	1 May 2010 to 30 April 2013; 3 year study period; daily time step	West Germany
[9]	Modelling; In situ measurements	Sampling sites in Yun-Lin plan 1000 km ²	Saily (1991-1998)	Taiwan
[10]	Modelling plus various data	404 km ²	Annual simulations (daily time steps)	Ipswich River basin, U.S.
[11]	In situ measurements (sap flow), Empirical Formulas,	2500 m ²	Daily (hourly) 1996	Tropical woodland, Northern Australia
[12]	In situ measurements	27 ha	Hourly/ sub hourly	South France
[13]	CATHY model, in situ measurements, sap flow	0.8 and 0.5 km ²	Hourly, 2011-2014	South-eastern Australia

[14]	Modeling (PArFlow); in site measurements	38.5 ha	Hourly/sub-hourly	Germany
[15]	Modeling (TOPMODEL)	8 ha - 13 ha	Hourly	Zamora-Chinchiye, Ecuador
[16]	Remote sensing	35058-1353269 km ²	Annual (monthly)	Major US rivers
[17]	Modeling, in situ measurements	38 ha	Annual (monthly)	Rur, Germany
[18]	In situ measurement (including water table); Formulas;	180 ha	Annual 2003-2004 (monthly)	Lowland Southeast U.S.
[19]	Modeling Single trees measurements	Single trees	daily	Swabian Alb, Germany
[20]	In situ measurements	An alluvial fan	Events	South Australia
[21]	Modeling (GEOtop); in situ measurements	55 km ²	Hourly	Germany
[22]	In situ observation of precipitation, soil water, evapotranspiration, streamflow, groundwater	Area 1.77 km ²	Six years (1958-1964); monthly time steps (?)	Southern Sweden
[23]	Modeling (GSFlow)	54 km ²	daily	Nevada, U.S.
[24]	In situ measures (rainfall, streamflow, throughfall, TDR etc.)	Single trees (10 x 10 m - 20 x 16 m)	Annual	Gabumbal State Forest, Queensland, Australia
[25]	Modelling	0.01 km ²	Monthly	North-central Colorado and Chichasha, Oklahoma, U.S.
[26]	Modelling, observed monthly rainfall	Collie River Basin (2545 km ²)	Monthly and daily	Semiarid western Australia
[27]	Satellite measurements (especially GRACE)	The whole northern hemisphere	Annual (2003-2009)	Eurasian Pan-Arctic basins
[28]	Modeling (GEOtop); in situ measurements	76 ha	Hourly/sub-hourly	Ireland
[29]	Precipitation and discharge data combined with simple water balance equation model	Area 103 ha	17 years (at annual scale)	Sierra-Nevada (California)

[30]	Reanalysis	Global Earth	Annual(1995-2005)	Global Earth
[31]	In situ data	Single points	Two years (sub-hourly)	Tennessee, U.S.
[32]	Combination of observations (station and gridded for precipitation) and the global reanalyses (NCEP/NCAR) data	Amazon River Basin	For a period of 1970-1999; at daily time step	Amazon river basin
[33]	ParFlow model	6.3 million km ² ; 1km resolution	one year at hourly time step	Major river basins in North America (US)
[34]	In situ measurements of hourly precipitation, soil and air temperature, humidity, global radiation, wind speed and wind direction	Area 6 ha; 20 m X 20 m	hourly data	Artificial Chicken Creek catchment (East Germany)
[35]	Empirical formulas;	27 km ²	daily (1978-1996)	Curtin Catchment, Canberra, Australia
[36]	Satellite data integration method	Spatial resolution: 0.5°; Mississippi river basin closed at Vicksburg gauging station (2,964,255 km ²)	at monthly time scale	Mississippi river
[37]	In situ measurements	16.7 ha	Hourly	Panama
[38]	Experimental sites	Site	Five census periods	Austria-France-Switzerland
[39]	Modeling; in situ measurements	36-175 km ²	daily (2009-2012)	Panama
[40]	Remote Sensing (TRMM, MOD16, GRACE); modelling	2000000 km ²	Yearly (2003-2010)	Brazilian Cerrado
[41]	Ensemble Kalman filter data assimilation of observation and VIC land surface model	Area 75000 km ²	Monthly (daily)	Southern Great Plan region of USA
[42]	In situ measurements of precipitation, evapotranspiration, soil moisture, snow	Filed scale (500X500 meter) for two years	Monthly (2013-2014)	Saskatchewan (Canada)

[43]	In situ measurements	1 ha	hourly/sub-hourly	Germany
[44]	Remote Sensing; reanalysis	Global Earth	Annual	Earth
[45]	Radiosonde observations	Large scale	Monthly and annual time steps over 20 yrs period	Central United States
[46]	Multiple satellite data and satellite merging technique	Large scale	Monthly (for 2003-2006)	Major global rivers basins
[47]	In situ measurements in Forest	Forest stand	Monthly (1984-1986)	Viterbo, Italy
[48]	In-situ measures (radiation, precip, surface runoff, soil water content, ET/Eddy Covariance)	Few ha	Annual (2004-2008)	Walnut Gulch Experimental site
[49]	Modelling; in situ data	176-2344 km ²	Monthly (daily)	Oklahoma, Mississippi, North Carolina, U.S.
[50]	In situ measurements (cosmic ray neutron sensing, distribute sensor networks)	0.012 and 0.046 km ²	(Annual) hourly (2013-2014)	Tucson, Arizona, U.S.
[51]	Remote sensing data (evaluated by North American Land Data Assimilation System (NLDAS) and atmospheric reanalysis data taken from the North American Regional Reanalysis (NARR))	Mississippi	Monthly time steps (for two years 2003-2005)	Mississippi basin
[52]	Modelling; daily satellite images	0.52-37.4 km ²	daily/hourly	Western Australia
[53]	In situ measurements	95 ha	daily	Ireland
[54]	Estimation of the Surface Water Budget of the La Plata Basin	La Plata Basin (189300 to 2 051 729 km ²)	Annual (daily)	South America
[55]	Micrometeorological tower, ground measurements, neutron probe	6.58 km ²	Monthly (2001-2004)	Amazonian micro-catchment close to Manaus (BZ)
[56]	Forest stands measurements (sapflow, etc), LAI and empirical formulas (ash and hazel trees)	Single plants	Annual	Central Highlands, Australia

[57]	Modeling (WASim-ETH), down-scaled meteo data, Remote Sensing	94000 km ² (1 km x 1 km)	Annual	White Volta Catchment
[58]	In-situ measurement (discharge at 15-min; precipitation at hourly; ET estimated P-Q at annual scale)	Area 97.5 ha; Walker Branch Watershed	Water balance at annual time scale	Walker Branch Watershed (US)
[59]	Catchment Pinus Radiata. Measurements; Empirical Formulas.	8.7 ha	Hourly	D. Don Forest, North Island, New Zealand
[60]	In situ observation (long-term (1979-2008) datasets developed for P by McKenney et al. (2011), ET by Wang et al. (2013), E0 by Wang and Yang (2011), TWS by Lambert et al. (2013), as well as the in situ Q)	Australia, Lake Eyre basin	Annual (1979-2008)	Australia
[61]	Budyko hypothesis	272 - 94800 km ²	Annual	Tibetan Plateau, River Haihe, China
[62]	Remote sensing, reanalysis, in situ observations	Continental scale	Annual (1982-2010)	Northern China
[63]	In situ of air temperature, wet-bulb temperature, precipitation, discharge, net radiation, wind speed, and snow depth were collected from	1.15km ²	Annual 1988-1998 (daily)	Headwater basin of the Uryu River (Japan)
[64]	Budyko framework	5- 2000 km ²	Mean Annual (monthly, daily)	China

2. INFORMATION ABOUT THE DATA SET

The NewAge-JGrass system is applied to the Posina river basin. It is a small catchment (116 km²), located in the the Alpine foothills of Veneto Region in Italy. The dem of the basin is available at [65] Its climate is characterised as wet, with an annual precipitation of 1645 millimeters and annual runoff of 1000 millimeters [66]. The coordinates and elevations of the hydro-meteorological stations are reported in table S2. The meteorological stations provide hourly rainfall and temperature data, and the hydrometer stations provide the hourly discharge data. The geographical characteristics of the three hydrometer stations are presented at table S2. Figure S1 shows the subbasins and channel links used in this study. Data for the Posina river basin were kindly provided by ARPA-Regione Veneto.

Fig. S1. The Posina basin and the HRU partition used for simulation. The triangle points are the discharge measurement stations. The location and elevation of the basin are described in Abera et al.submitted

Table S2. List of the meteorological stations and hydrometers used for meteorological (rainfall and temperature) spatial interpolation and rainfall-runoff model calibration and validation analysis in the Posina river basin. The last three stations are marked with a (*) to indicate that these are discharge gauging stations. The areas of the basin and subbasins draining to each hydrometer are given in brackets.

ID.	City	Z	X	Y
51	Folgaria UPO	1168	1668428	5086815
63	Lavarone UPO	1171	1674754	5089860
204	Brustol Velo d'Astico	328	1682121	5074661
206	Contrà Doppio Posina	725	1672938	5075022
208	Molini Laghi	597	1675208	5078024
210	Monte Summano	619	1687964	5069297
212	Passo Xomo Posina	1056	1674012	5071777
214	Pedescala	308	1683840	5079537
216	Valli del Pasubio	600	1672265	5069542
218	Castana Arsiero	430	1679369	5076164
201*	Rio Freddo at Valoje (22.24km ²)	390	1681507	5075248
202*	Posina at Stancari (116.2km ²)	388	1681524	5075140
203*	Posina at Bazzoni (38.82km ²)	453	1678208	5074606

All the data produced by this interplay of measures and simulation (up to 2011 included) were used to infer evapotranspiration. The 2012 hydrological budget was entirely forecasted for what regards discharges, evapotranspiration and water storage.

3. MODEL SET-UP

Figure S2 shows a simplified sketch on JGrass-NewAge model set-up.

Fig. S2. The workflow of model set-up for NewAge-JGrass hydrological model system. First, the elevation need to be processes to obtain the channel and the hillslopes according to the basin partition procedure. Then meteorological data, then is interpolated to each hillslopes according to different interpolation algorithms. Common ID is used to connect the channel links, hillslopes and point of interpolations (i.e centroids).

4. LIST OF NEWAGE-JGRASS COMPONENTS USED

Table S3. NewAge-JGrass Hydrological modelling components: they range from hydrological pre-processing, such as topographic and hydrological conditioning, to automatic model parameter optimization components. The components in bold are the ones used in this study

Role	Component Name	Description
Basin hillslope-link partitioning	GIS spatial toolbox and Horton Machine	A GIS spatial toolbox that uses DEM to extract basin, hillslopes, and channel links for NewAge-JGrass set-up. The channel partition is according to the Pfafstetter enumeration system [67, 68]
Data interpolation	Kriging , Inverse Distance Weighting, and JAMI	Interpolates meteorological data from meteorological stations to points of interest according to a variety of kriging algorithms [69–72], Inverse Distance Weighting [73]
Energy balance	Shortwave radiation, Longwave radiation model	Calculate shortwave and longwave radiation, respectively, from topographic and atmospheric data [74–76].
Evapotranspiration	Penman-Monteith, Priestly-Taylor , Fao-Evapotranspiration	Estimates evapotranspiration using Penman-Monteith [77], Priestly-Taylor [78], and Fao-Evapotranspiration [79] options
Runoff	ADIGE (Hymod)	Estimates runoff based on Hymod [80] algorithm
Optimization	Particle Swarm Optimization , DREAM, LUCA	Calibrate model parameters according to Particle Swarm Optimization [81], DREAM [82], LUCA [83] algorithms respectively.

5. MODIS SNOW ALBEDO PROCESSING FOR SWE MODEL CALIBRATION

The daily standard snow products of Terra and Aqua MODIS products, i.e. MOD10A1 and MYD10A1 (V005) [84] are used for calibration of snowfall-rainfall separation model. Both products are downloaded from NASA, which is distributed through the National Snow and Ice Data Center in Boulder, Colorado [85] at <http://modis-snow-ice.gsfc.nasa.gov>. Terra (MOD10A1) is collected since February 2000 while Aqua (MYD10A1) is since June 2002. The study basin is covered by the h18v04 MODIS tile. The technical steps on MODIS snow products processing is similar to that described by [86].

First the MOD10A1 fractional snow cover (FSc) of the study area is used. It provides the percentage coverage (0-100%) of a pixel with snow. If MOD10A1 does not provide FSc estimates due to any reason, it is replaced with the MYD10A1 for that particular time steps or pixel. This helps to produce much less “no values” and eliminates clouds, providing a much more useful image than the one obtained by MOD10A1 or MYD10A1 alone, e.g. [87].

The FSc itself has advantages over the snow/no-snow data, which is often used in routine applications. It provides the percentage of each pixel (or any aggregated scale) covered by the snow. This helps the decision on the discriminating threshold between snow/no-snow binary data, based on the scale, location and purpose of the application. Usually, to get snow cover information, a threshold

in FSc is used. In this study the threshold is set at 10%. Therefore, values of FSc below 10% are set not having snow and pixels with FSc larger than 10% are considered as snow covered. Then the snow/no-snow based distributed information is used to optimize the rainfall-snowfall separation algorithm parameters.

Snow albedo, the ratio of outgoing to incoming radiation at the snow surface, is very sensitive to the snow cover and its properties and, therefore, it also can be used as a geophysical signature for the estimation the SWE [88]. Albedo is extracted from the MODIS (MOD10A1 and MYD10A1 (V005)) snow product. It is downloaded from NASA, which is distributed through the National Snow and Ice Data Center in Boulder, Colorado [85]. The extraction is from both products, i.e. if MOD10A1 does not provide snow albedo data for a particular time step or pixel, it is replaced by the MYD10A1 snow albedo value. Subsequently the snow albedo values at pixel level are aggregated at HRU level. the operation is repeated for daily time steps and 7 years (2000-2006). This transformed data set is used for the estimation of the JGrass-NewAGE parameters, as described in the main text.

6. ADIGE MODEL

The NewAge component estimating runoff is called ADIGE. It is made by many Hymods [80], one for each HRU in which the basin is subdivided. Furthermore, ADIGE includes a routing model along the river network that connects the HRUs [89]. The Hymod core of the component is a conceptual, rainfall-runoff, model that separates a quick (shallow) flux from a slower (deeper) one. The first accounts for surface runoff by using three linear reservoirs, the latter accounts for subsurface storm flow with one single linear reservoir [80, 89, 90]. Groundwater is modeled with an additional storage. Essential to Hymod's calculation is the estimation of the water "losses" by ET. Detailed descriptions of the Hymod model are provided in many researches [80, 89, 91, 92] and summarised in the following paragraphs.

In Hymod, each HRU, is supposed to be a composition of storages of capability C [L] according to distribution [80]:

$$F(C < c) = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{c}{C_{max}}\right)^{B_{exp}} \quad (\text{S1})$$

where $F(C)$ represents the cumulative probability of a certain water storage capacity, C ; C_{max} is the largest water storage capacity within each hillslope and B_{exp} is the degree of variability in the storage capacity.

As shown in the schematic diagram (figure S3), the precipitation exceeding C_{max} is sent directly to the volume available for surface runoff. If we call the precipitation volume in a time interval Δt , $P(t) := J(t)\Delta t$, then this "direct" runoff can be estimated according to:

$$R_H(t) = \max(0, J(t) + C(t) - C_{max}) \quad (\text{S2})$$

where $C(t)$ defines the fraction of storages already filled at time t . The latter equation is true for any precipitation and storage level, even when the maximum storage C_{max} is not exceeded. When precipitation does not exceed C_{max} runoff volume can be produced by filling some of the smaller storages. To which extent this happens, can be derived by the knowledge of the storage distribution, eq. (S1), the initial storage $C(t)$ and the precipitation $P(t)$. This residual runoff is, in fact, given by:

$$R(t) = \int_{C(t)}^{\min(C(t)+J(t), C_{max})} F(c) dc \quad (\text{S3})$$

An analytic expressions for the integral in Eq. (S3) is available, which makes the computation easier. Water in storage is made available for evapotranspiration. Water going into the runoff volume, i.e.

Fig. S3. schematic diagram of hymod model (adapted from [91])

$R(t)$ and R_H , is further subdivided into a surface runoff volume and subsurface storm runoff. Surface runoff, in turn, is composed by the whole of $R_H(t)$ and part of $R(t)$, and $R(t)$ is split according to a partition coefficient Θ such that the part $\Theta R(t)$ goes into surface runoff volume and $(1 - \Theta)$ into the subsurface storm runoff volume. In HyMOD, Θ is a calibration coefficient.

Finally, surface runoff volumes are routed through three linear reservoirs and subsurface storm runoff volumes is routed through a single linear reservoir. A summary of equations for the surface runoff is therefore:

$$\frac{dS_1(t)}{dt} = \Theta R(t) + R_H(t) - kS_1(t) \quad Q_1(t) = \frac{S_1(t)}{k} \quad (\text{S4})$$

where S_1 [L^3] is the storage in the first of the linear reservoirs, and k [T] is the mean residence time in each of the reservoirs. Then:

$$\frac{dS_i(t)}{dt} = Q_{i-1}(t) - kS_i(t) \quad Q_i(t) = \frac{S_i(t)}{k} \quad (\text{S5})$$

for the other two reservoirs, where S_i [L] with $i = 2, 3$ is the storage in the two remaining surface reservoirs. Subsurface storm runoff is then modelled by:

$$\frac{dS_{sub}}{dt} = (1 - \Theta)R(t) - k_{sub}S_{sub}(t) \quad (\text{S6})$$

where S_{sub} [L^3] is the storage in the subsurface storm-flow system and k_{sub} [T] is its mean residence time. A budget equation can be written for the groundwater system as:

$$\frac{dS_g(t)}{dt} = (J(t) - R(t) - R_H(t)) - ET(t) - Q_g(t) \quad (\text{S7})$$

where $S_g(t)$ [L^3] is the groundwater storage and $Q_g(t)$ the groundwater flow, which becomes surface flow at the closure of the HRU.

Summarizing, Hymod subdivides each HRU into three reservoirs: a groundwater reservoir, from where evapotranspiration and groundwater flow is allowed, a subsurface storm-water reservoir, and a surface runoff set of reservoirs. Partition of precipitation into the three reservoirs is obtained by a calibration coefficient, Θ , and the use of a probability distribution function of storage capacity, $F(c)$.

Notably Hymod provides not only a recipe for estimating the storage, $S(t)$, but also fully determines its variation, as in eq. (S5), Therefore, eq (S7) can be used to modulate the actual evapotranspiration estimation.

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